

PAVILION R1244

Designing and Building with Reused Components and Materials

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ABSTRACT

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction industry needs to significantly reduce the use of primary resources, CO₂ emissions and energy consumption. One promising approach is to extend building lifespans, also with the support of retrofitting measures.

A pioneering experimental adaptive high-rise building was developed as a flexible research platform to explore and validate methods for a simplified replacement of facades and building components based on their service life. In 2023, a new research facade was installed and the temporary timber and PVC-PES facade was dismantled. Reuse scenarios for the reclaimed materials were developed and tested through case studies, starting with the construction of a pavilion that explores and refines the concepts of form follows availability and design for disassembly.

The project employed a five-step methodology using digital tools for component cataloguing and design. The pavilion was designed following modularity and disassembly principles, showing potential for component reuse. Key findings show that extending component lifespan enhances resource efficiency, focusing on resource recovery and digital stock. Timber proved highly reusable, while membrane reuse faced challenges. Reversible bolt joints were analysed, adapted and implemented to boost reusability. The study stresses the importance of strategic material selection and reversible assembly in promoting sustainable construction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry can reduce future CO₂ emissions and reduce energy consumption by implementing retrofitting measures and extending building lifespans (Sobek, 2022). Since 2017, an interdisciplinary team of researchers has focused on adaptive skins and structures as a promising approach to reduce resource consumption and environmental impact. As a result of the first four years an experimental demonstrator building called D1244 (Figure 1) has been built in 2021 to showcase and experimentally validate the developed technologies and systems (Blandini et al., 2022).

Figure 1:
The experimental demonstrator high-rise D1244 in 2022 (copyright: R. Müller)

D1244 is also designed to allow for a substitution of facade and structural components, thus raising the flexibility in the research use, but also serving as a platform to investigate, improve and validate the application of the three R's principles (reduce, reuse, recycle) to facades and structures. The focus of the following work is on the reuse aspect. The first major conversion took place in 2023 with the replacement of the temporary facade on the ground floor with two newly developed adaptive facades (Blandini et al., 2024a) (Blandini et al., 2024b). The conversion of the second-floor facade followed in 2024 (Jeong et al., 2024). This process involved the disassembly of the temporary PVC-PES membrane facade, supported by timber profiles. Although D1244 was designed for disassembly, reuse scenarios for the building components and materials were not originally planned in detail. This is the motivation for launching a series of case studies, with the aim of developing and validating methods to improve the capacity of

components reuse. The first case study focuses on the construction of a multi-purpose pavilion using the reclaimed materials. The main question addressed is how effectively the individual facade components can be separated, considering the type and extent of damage they have sustained during the dismantling process with a particular focus on the effects of the joining techniques employed. The second related question is whether, or to what extent, the selected components need to be modified in order to be reused.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

It is imperative to shift from a linear “take-make-waste” model to a circular model in which resources are used in a sustainable approach. Industry 5.0 technologies and circular economy principles present a significant opportunity for the advancement of a sustainable built environment. Addressing the challenges inherent in the AEC industry can involve the implementation of circular strategies, such as service life enhancement of materials, rehabilitation, dis- and reassembly, design for reuse, and implementation of regenerative design (De Wolf et al., 2024b). Circular economy can be achieved through four resource strategies (Çetin et al., 2021) (Konietzko et al., 2020): Narrowing the loop by increasing efficiency, slowing the loop by extending product lifespans and reducing consumption, closing the loop through reuse and efficient recycling, and regenerating the loop by enhancing environmental and societal well-being.

In this regard, closing the loop is crucial, as reusability allows materials to retain their original form and value (ISO 20887, 2020). Reuse is often more beneficial than recycling, as greenhouse gas emissions can be reduced by using components in their original state (Minunno et al., 2020). To achieve comprehensive reuse, two key approaches should be considered. Firstly, whenever feasible, components and materials from deconstructed existing buildings should be reused. Secondly, accurate reuse scenarios should be planned and applied already during the design phase for new buildings (John and Stark, 2021).

To facilitate the reuse of building components, it is recommended to develop scenarios for potential or anticipated future adaptations (Dodd et al., 2021). Brütting et al. propose an innovative reuse strategy through the development of a modular system that allows the construction of a range of structures using different configurations of adaptable modular elements. By following the principle of form follows availability, structures can be designed to reuse components in their original form and characteristics. Although this approach presents challenges, the use of digital tools offers the potential to address them effectively (Brütting et al., 2019).

Coordinating the disassembly of an existing building with the construction of a new building presents several challenges. Despite technical obstacles, successful sustainable building models have been

developed and implemented (De Wolf et al., 2024a). A study involving demolition industry experts highlighted two critical measures for facilitating low-damage deconstruction: providing comprehensive building data, including as-built and deconstruction plans, and ensuring early design decisions which support the proper separation of components, known as design for disassembly (DfD) (Charlson, 2013). Therefore, a modular design holds significant potential for minimizing waste and enhancing efficiency in the systematic assembly and disassembly of building components. As a crucial strategy within DfD, modularity offers systematic guidance for architecture, from initial conception to its end-of-life stage (Arisya and Suryantini, 2021).

The European Commission highlights three key aspects for promoting circularity: ease of recovery, reuse and recycling. Ease of recovery ensures that building components are independent, easily separable and connected with simple, reversible joints. Ease of reuse allows for functional adaptability and incorporates elements with standard dimensions. Ease of recycling prioritizes homogeneous, separable and recyclable materials. An ISO standard also outlines key disassembly criteria that need to be considered in the design, such as: ease of access to the components, independence of the components from each other, no unnecessary surface treatments, simplicity, standardization and dismantling safety (ISO 20887, 2020).

In order to enhance sustainability in construction, it is recommended that components are sourced close to the construction site (Federal Foundation of Baukultur, 2023). It is of the utmost importance to plan the dismantling and logistics of a construction project meticulously in order to minimise the amount of waste produced. Materials should be selected based on their potential for future demand and reuse (ISO 20887, 2020). The implementation of computational design for the management of building component inventories, can further facilitate this process (Hillebrandt, 2019). Furthermore, the transition from traditional computer-aided design (CAD) to building information modelling (BIM), which integrates non-geometric component data into detailed three-dimensional models (Leistner et al., 2022), can significantly enhance the scope and efficiency of material reuse.

3. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

A 5-step methodology was developed for the design and construction of reuse research projects (Figure 2). The pavilion serves as a case study for reusing components that were not part of a defined reuse concept in the original design of the deconstructed building. The methodology may need to be adapted for anticipated reuse projects.

Figure 2:
Methodology

3.1. RESOURCE RECOVERY

In 2023, the facades of the ground and first floor were dismantled to facilitate the installation of two new adaptive skins (Blandini et al., 2024b). Although the components were neither categorized nor labelled for potential reuse, the deconstruction process played a crucial role in advancing the understanding of facade deconstruction techniques. It also provided the construction team with essential knowledge and practical skills and laid a solid foundation for efficiently managing future dismantling of the temporary facades.

Figure 3:
Recording of the mined
materials and components

3.2. BUILDING STOCK DIGITALIZATION

A student design studio was set up, to digitalise the building stock, design and build a multi-purpose pavilion out of the dismantled pieces. The initial goal was to digitally catalogue the disassembled building stock (Figure 3). This process began with organizing components from disassembled facades to measure and to assess them. An online Excel spreadsheet was created, giving each component a unique identifier. Details like dimensions, material type, condition (1 = good, 3 = poor), and photos were recorded. Each identifier was linked to a QR code, allowing easy mobile access to component information. Another key objective was recording the dimensions of the timber components in a 3D model. A parametric approach with Rhinoceros 3D and Grasshopper was employed, linking the Excel file (.xlsx/.csv) to automatically generate volumetric representations based on dimensions (width, height, length) and grouping them by size for stock visualization (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Building Stock digitalization workflow

3.3. DESIGN PROCESS

The main goal of the established design studio was to reuse the reclaimed components to create a sheltered pavilion next to the high-rise, serving as a multi-functional space for presentations and catering during events. To achieve this, the design focused on the principles of modularity, design for disassembly, and form follows availability principles. Interdisciplinary collaboration was key for the design of Pavilion R1244: several workshops between the students and professionals from architecture, structural engineering, and carpentry supported the process.

Through iterative design loops (Figure 5), the most promising pavilion design emerged as a flexible, irregular pentagonal space with an adaptable open floor plan. It features a simple, lightweight, tensegrity-inspired roof supported by three aerial columns and cables, creating a large rigid frame. This frame connects to four columns, enhancing the open space and creating a floating corner effect. In the final design the structural system was optimized and the connections were simplified. Thorough static analysis was essential to consider component capacity and seasonal factors such as wind and snow.

Figure 5:
Preparation of model and sketches within the Design Studio

3.4. DIGITAL DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURING

During the group design phase, each interdisciplinary team used different digital tools. Once the final design was selected (Figure 6), Rhinoceros 3D (Rhino) was used to integrate all the models into a comprehensive 3D model, allowing detailed technical adjustments and connections to be made. To streamline construction documentation and planning, a workflow was established between Rhino and Revit using the Rhino.Inside.Revit plug-in. This setup facilitated ongoing 3D updates in Rhino, while conveniently updating plans in Revit. This workflow proved to be effective; for example, the membrane sections were deconstructed in Rhino, while Revit provided the technical documentation for each component and the required connections between them. Similarly, the precise positioning of holes in the wooden columns and beams was mapped in Rhino, with detailed plans generated in Revit.

3.5. CONSTRUCTION

The carefully designed, fully demountable and reusable pavilion, was built with a strong focus on practicality. Precision was crucial in the

preparation of the structure to ensure that the membrane could be cut accurately whilst achieving the desired aesthetic results. The assembly process began with the installation of the upper main beams, followed by the attachment of tension cables and flying struts (Figure 7).

Figure 6:
**Rendering of Pavilion R1244
prior to Construction**

Figure 7:
**Roof during construction in
July 2024**

The cables were custom spliced to length and pretensioned via a simple ratchet strap mechanism in the beam corners to reduce deformations of the pavilion. The membrane was wrapped around the canopy frame and secured by clamping with wooden battens. Once the roof assembly was complete, the columns were constructed using proven and demountable timber pincer techniques. The roof was then lifted using a forklift and scaffolding to facilitate the connection of the columns. The column base points were made of reused steel footers. Slotted plates were welded to the footers and an anti-corrosion coating was added. Each base was anchored to the concrete floor to ensure structural integrity.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS / FINDINGS

This case study examines how to extend the life of building components in a resource-efficient manner, with a focus on initially not considered reuse projects. A 5-step methodology to guide the design and construction of the project is used, focusing on ease of recovery and reuse. While the application of lightweight principles as a means of reducing resource consumption is always relevant and recycling is undeniably important, this paper prioritises the approach of component reuse. Overall, the implementation of these strategies presents significant challenges, mainly due to the different levels of modification required for the reclaimed components. The case study revealed that the ease of recovery varies greatly depending on the specific materials and components involved. Consequently, no generalised conclusions can be drawn for the project as a whole, but each material group must be analysed individually, as detailed below (Figure 8).

4.1. RESOURCE RECOVERY

The main structure of the facade, consisting of standard rectangular timber profiles, suffered partial damage during dismantling due to the assembly techniques used. As a result, certain profiles had to be reprocessed or shortened, due to damage to allow for more efficient reuse. Other elements were strategically reused depending on their shape. For example, the original angled timber beams naturally shaped the membrane of the pavilion roof. The main horizontal beams of the temporary facade were reused without any modification as benches at the platform entrance (Figure 9).

The membrane suffered partial damage during dismantling due to poor sequencing, planning and documentation of the disassembly process. The sections of the membrane that had been properly disassembled showed vertical perforations from staple removal. As a solution, the dismantled sections of membrane, approximately 3x5 metres each, were creatively arranged to resemble the veins of a leaf.

Figure 8: Case study findings

The new membranes were triple stitched for increased stability and durability. Any perforations were sealed using leftover material, minimising the need for new purchases.

The fasteners presented a significant challenge. Although the threaded bolts securing the facade to the steel structure were easy to unscrew and remained undamaged, other fasteners proved more difficult to remove. Wood screws were used to join the timber profiles, many of which were difficult to remove due to their length, diameter and angle of insertion.

Many screws were bent or damaged during removal, making them unsuitable for reuse. Similarly, the staples used to secure the membrane to the timber could be extracted, but perforated the membrane and were destroyed in the process.

Figure 9:
Benches at the platform entrance

After dismantling, materials were tagged with the previously described QR codes to facilitate future identification and documentation of their characteristics. The inventory showed that tagging components and integrating the data into a digital material database is a straightforward process. However, methodological improvements are possible. Forward planning could further simplify this process, with an emphasis on integrating reuse scenarios during the design phase to allow for structured disassembly and storage. The authors firmly believe that future design, dismantling, accurate component labelling and failure assessment would benefit from the use of data potentially integrated into a Building Information Model (BIM).

4.2. COMPONENT REUSE

The case study revealed that the potential for reuse, similar to the ease of recovery discussed in Chapter 4.1, varies significantly depending on the materials of the components. The design of the pavilion aims to maximize the use of available disassembled timber profiles by modifying the original components as minimal as possible, while still meeting the programmatic requirements (Figure 11).

Figure 10:
1- Temporary facades components, 2- Available stock, 3- Selected stock, 4- Pavilion and bench

Figure 11:
Components modification

Where adjustments to the timber were required due to damage caused during the dismantling process, the timber could be shortened or lengthened using adhesives. It was found that working with and reusing the timber required minimal specialist knowledge and only basic tools. In contrast, reinforcing the perforated areas of the membrane with bonded cover strips proved challenging due to the specific adhesives required for the membrane surface coating. This process resulted in a directional strip pattern which imposed significant design and construction requirements on the roof (Figure 12). Most of the fasteners removed during the process were damaged and unsuitable for reuse. To tackle this issue, reversible connections utilizing more robust fasteners were developed for the pavilion's construction. Simple pincer joints combined with durable threaded bolts were employed, enabling easy assembly and disassembly, while also facilitating future reuse. Employing a BIM model of the deconstructed building would enhance the potential for reuse. This approach would support optimized reusability through the optional application of a parametric model.

Figure 12:
The membrane arrangement incorporates a directional pattern, using the spacing and perforation of the disassembled facade to mimic the delicate veins of a leaf

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The pavilion R1244 (Figure 13) serves as a case study to examine the potential for extending the lifespan of building components, evaluating assembly methods to ensure future ease of disassembly and reuse. It is apparent that following the principles of modularity and design for disassembly -and therefore considering a potential re-assembly of components from the outset of a project- increases the effectiveness of reuse. However, in some cases, the concept of form follows availability is difficult to achieve without adapting the respective components. Reusing components without any modification (100% reuse) is feasible in certain applications, however to achieve more reuse in the future, components may need to be partially adapted or reconfigured.

Unprocessed timber profiles, due to their standard dimensions and widespread availability, offer significant potential for re-use with minimal loss of value. In some cases, however, minor modifications may be required to improve joints and enhance functionality in new applications. For membrane reuse, it is recommended that perforation be avoided and that clamping methods be used instead, as surface coatings make reuse difficult. Fasteners should be robust to increase reuse rates. While bolted and screwed joints are not inherently reversible, their potential for disassembly and reusability is context dependent.

In conclusion, resource-efficient construction can be achieved through strategic material selection and reversible, non-destructive assembly methods that increase the longevity and reusability of

building components. Generally, the analysis of the dismantled temporary facades is based on a limited scope, focusing on just three materials. Existing buildings, however, are often much more complex, incorporating a wide range of materials and highly specific components. Therefore, it is important to expand the scope of future studies to include additional materials.

In a second case study, the components from the dismantled facades will be reused for the design and construction of a modular, adaptable, and reversible vertical extension system. This system will be implemented on top of an existing building in the immediate vicinity. The goal is to create a load-bearing structure using the disassembled timber profiles, involving the development of reversible, adaptable, and robust connections. Components and materials from other dismantling projects will be included to create roofing and facade prototypes in order to broaden the reusability analysis.

Figure 13:
Pavilion R1244 in use

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PROJECT VIDEO

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